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Abstract

Contrastive linguistics, a branch of comparative linguistics, emerged as a distinct field in the last quarter of the 20th century, developing its own objectives and methods for studying languages. Contrastive linguistics is characterized primarily by its narrower focus and high level of detail, focusing primarily on differences rather than similarities between languages, and primarily examining differences within just two languages. Furthermore, for comparison of a specific language pair, whether the languages are related or not is irrelevant. Contrastive linguistics also differs from other typological approaches in that it operates across a relatively broad range of linguistic structure.

Keywords: contrastive linguistics, goal of contrastive analysis, contrastive studies, theoretical and applied linguistics.

The term "contrastive linguistics" was formulated by Benjamin Lee Whorf in his article "Languages and Logic", published in 1941. He drew a distinction between comparative and contrastive linguistics, arguing that contrastive linguistics would play a very important role in linguistic research, and defining it as a scientific discipline that "outlines the most important differences between languages in the areas of grammar, logic, and the general analysis of accumulated linguistic experience" [4, p. 240].

To conduct interlingual/intralingual and intercultural/intracultural comparisons in contrastive linguistics, most researchers use the term "contrastive analysis," although other formulations of this phenomenon can be found in the linguistic literature. For example, "parallel description of languages," "differential study of languages," "differential description of languages," "analytical comparison of languages," "interlingual comparison of languages," "descriptive comparison of languages," etc.

The goal of contrastive analysis is to compare linguistic and sociocultural data across a range of languages or individual languages in order to identify patterns, categories, and features that reflect the specificity of a particular language, as well as typological and/or universal patterns, categories, and features common to a range of languages. An integral part of contrastive research is the analysis of interlingual correspondences, which provides a better understanding of structural and functional divergence.

Early contrastive studies focused only on phonology, grammar, and vocabulary, and were therefore called micro-linguistic contrastive analysis [1, p. 61]. Here are examples of questions that needed to be answered in such an analysis:

- Which consonant phonemes in language X correspond to the consonant phonemes in language Y?
- How do they differ in composition, realization, and distribution?

– What is the system of grammatical tenses in languages X and Y?

Contrast analysis typically involves four steps:

description (the language structures selected for comparison are comprehensively described and analyzed according to the linguistic model chosen for this purpose);

selection of material for comparison (a decision is made about which aspects of the two languages will be compared, since it is impossible to compare everything at once in one study);

comparison (the process of contrastive analysis itself takes place, during which differences and similarities in the compared language systems are identified);

forecasting (explanations are given about which areas of the language being studied may encounter problems).

Many linguist researchers have their own views on how contrastive analysis should be conducted. For example, linguist K. James believes that the process of contrastive analysis consists of two stages: "the description stage, where each of the languages under consideration is described separately at a certain level, and the comparison stage, where the languages under consideration are compared" [1, p. 233].

In 1998, E. Chesterman proposed his own methodology for conducting contrastive analysis, arguing that the most objective information can be obtained through a continuous process of working on the problem. In his work, "Contrastive Functional Analysis," he writes that contrastive analysis includes two main processes—description and comparison—which are implemented in four main stages: 1) data collection; 2) description of languages; 3) replenishment of data as needed; 4) presentation of the identified differences between languages [2, p. 52]. The description of the studied structures of the languages under consideration must be based on the same model in order to conduct an objective analysis. In this regard, E. Chesterman puts forward a detailed methodology for comparing languages:

1) collection of primary data, on the basis of which the proposed hypotheses should be tested. The initial information should include all cases of language use by people speaking the languages under study;

2) establishment of a criterion based on apparent similarity of any kind;

3) establishment of the nature of the comparison, the similarity of the preliminary hypothesis; and the formulation of a basis for it;

4) testing the hypothesis: determining the conditions for its acceptance or rejection. This process usually includes the selection of theoretical foundations, primary and additional material, the use of parallel corpora of texts, and analysis of errors and behavior of people speaking the languages under study;

5) formulation of a revised hypothesis;

6) testing the revised hypothesis [2, p. 68].

The undoubted task of a contrastive researcher is to create conditions under which the obtained results are justified. Depending on the comparison criterion, these conditions may be syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, stylistic, contextual, etc.

In his monograph "A Comparative Typology of English and German – Unifying the Contrasts," the English linguist John Hawkins used a holistic approach to pairwise comparison of languages, attempting to identify the relationship between the characteristics of certain grammatical subsystems in order to find general principles explaining the existence of interlingual divergences. The object of his research was the English and German languages, which he examined "from a universal typological point of view" in search of "unified generalizations underlying the differences between significant subsystems of languages" [3, pp. 3-4]. Although J. Hawkins's idea of a holistic approach to pairwise comparison of languages was not seriously used by other linguists, his research had a huge influence on the field of contrastive linguistics as a whole, defining it as a type of linguistic comparison that is self-sufficient in itself, without setting specific goals related to the study of a foreign language.

There are two types of contrastive studies: theoretical and applied. Theoretical contrastive studies provide a comprehensive and exhaustive analysis of the phonology, semantics, and syntax of the languages in question, provide suitable models for comparison, specify the elements to be compared, and the method for performing the comparison.

Applied contrastive studies are closely related to applied linguistics. They rely on the results of theoretical contrastive studies to provide a basis for comparing languages. They provide key information for teaching bilingual analysis and translation, diagnosing potential problems in acquiring the target language.

One of the key concepts of contrastive linguistics is the criterion of comparison. Before comparing languages, a linguist must determine what can be compared in the languages under consideration. Traditionally, there are three main approaches to approaching the problem of comparability. Initially, the criterion of comparison was established either at the semantic or grammatical level. The third method of establishing the criterion of comparison involves defining equivalence,

similarity, and difference relationships in the languages under consideration.

The concept of "equivalence" came to contrastive linguistics from translation studies, where it implies translation equivalence. When establishing the level of equivalence between the categories being compared in the languages being compared, concepts such as "lack of equivalence," "equivalence," and "complete equivalence" are used.

When discussing equivalence in contrastive linguistics, it is assumed that there is a common denominator by which comparisons can be made. This denominator is called the *tertium comparationis*, which means "basis for comparison" in Latin, and is a prerequisite for any consistent study of similarities and differences between languages. In classical contrastive analysis, the basis for comparison can be found within either the formal or semantic approaches to comparison. In the former, similarity is established through formal correspondence, which traces how the form features of the source language text are reproduced in the target language. In the case of the semantic approach, however, judgments regarding structural similarity depend largely on translation.

Contrastive description of languages can be carried out at all levels of language structure: phonological, morphological, lexical, phraseological, syntactic, textual through the prism of structural and cognitive approaches.

Contrastive linguistics, which has established contrastive analysis as a distinct field, is currently gaining momentum. The scope and depth of its research is only growing, and the diversity of practical and theoretical approaches is impressive. Modern linguistic approaches and cutting-edge technologies have opened up new horizons and avenues for contrastive linguistics in the implementation of contrastive analysis.

Thus, it can be said that at the present time, contrastive linguistics reflects fundamental concepts of language that have changed over time, and the goals and objectives of research have been revised.

References

1. James, K. *Contrastive Analysis* / K. James // *New in Foreign Linguistics*. Issue XXV. *Contrastive Linguistics: Translations / Comp.* by V.P. Neroznak; General editorship and introduction by V.G. Gak. – Moscow: Progress, 1989. – 440 p.
2. Chesterman, A. *Contrastive Functional Analysis* / A. Chesterman. – Amsterdam: Benjamins, 1998. – 230 p.
3. Hawkins, J.A. *Comparative Typology of English and German. Unifying the Contrasts* / J. Hawkins. – London: Croom Helm. Hawkins, 1986. – 244 p.
4. Whorf, B.L. *Language, Thought and Reality* / B.L. Whorf. – Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press, 1967. – 290 p.